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International practice of socially responsible investment: analysis of current trends

KEYWORDS

socially responsible investing,
SRI,
ESG standards,
SRI efficiency assessment,
startup,
venture investment

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of this article lies in the fact that the modern stock market is a dynamic and constantly evolving system that reacts swiftly to changes in the external environment. In recent years, global events have significantly heightened unpredictability and volatility in development processes, profoundly influencing the growth of socially responsible investing within this market segment.

Materials and methods. The research materials included scientific publications and articles, particularly studies and reviews from journals in the fields of economics, finance, and sustainable development, with a focus on socially responsible investing (SRI) and ESG factors. The methodological foundation of the study was based on general scientific methods such as analysis and synthesis, and the integration of historical and logical approaches, as well as specific evaluative techniques, including the observation of key indicators and expert assessments.

Results. The dynamics of the global socially responsible investment (SRI) market are examined, with particular attention given to the primary forms of state support for SRI in foreign countries, which represent a key component of the effective functioning of the SRI ecosystem. The main challenges facing the SRI market at the current stage are also identified. A critical issue in the development of the SRI market today is the absence of a universally accepted and integrated methodology, along with standardized frameworks and evaluation methods for tracking the allocation of securities and the use of proceeds in alignment with ESG objectives. This gap complicates the assessment of SRI effectiveness, increases the risk of greenwashing, and undermines investor confidence in SRI instruments. The development of a unified approach to evaluating the effectiveness of SRI – together with the establishment of standardized criteria and principles for responsible investment – will help improve social welfare, address environmental challenges, and support more effective and sustainable economic development globally.

Conclusion. At the current stage, the socially responsible investment (SRI) market is not merely emerging as a new segment of the broader investment landscape; it also reflects a fundamental transformation in the model of interaction between business, society, and the state. SRI is increasingly functioning as a kind of “auto-calibration tool” that facilitates the attainment of a new, stable equilibrium within national economic systems, aligned with global dynamics. This, in turn, contributes to addressing environmental and social challenges and supports the more effective and sustainable economic development of individual countries.

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INTRODUCTION

The turbulent events of the twentieth century brought about significant changes in the economic systems and structures of many countries, driven not only by efforts to improve models of economic development but also by profound military, political, and social upheavals. These rapid shifts in the social environment contributed to the emergence and advancement of the concept of socially responsible investing (SRI), which has since evolved within the broader framework of the sustainable development paradigm. The phenomenon of socially responsible investment reflects a growing investor interest in non-financial factors – particularly social, environmental, and ethical considerations. At its core, SRI aims to achieve measurable, and ideally maximized, social, environmental, and financial returns on invested capital. As such, it represents the next stage in the evolution of both capital markets and socially oriented practices. In the context of rising social inequality and shrinking public budgets, the mechanism of socially responsible investment (hereinafter referred to as SRI) is increasingly viewed as a tool for attracting private capital to serve public purposes.

Thus, in the modern world, an increasing number of investors are paying attention to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) aspects when making investment decisions. Studying foreign experiences will help understand how socially responsible investment (SRI) contributes to achieving sustainable development goals. Studying the knowledge of foreign countries will allow us to identify the most successful SRI models and strategies that can be adapted and applied in other regions. The analysis of foreign experience will help track current trends in SRI, such as the development of green bonds and investments in renewable energy sources, among others.

The purpose of this research is to analyze the dynamics, challenges, and prospects of the global socially responsible investment market at its current stage of development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research goals were achieved through a study of scientific works on this subject by specialists, including E. V. Altukhova, E. P. Ermakova, X. Chen, J. M. Puaschunder, N. Taher, and J. Tan.

The research materials consisted of scientific publications and articles, including studies and reviews in scientific journals on economics, finance, and sustainable

development, specifically those focused on SRI and ESG factors (Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Eurasian Studies in Business and Economics, Empirical Economics, Journal of Financial Economics).

The article also uses statistical and analytical reviews of international organizations and corporations related to the study of the impact of ESG transformation on the securities market (UNCTAD, GSIA, HSBC Holdings plc (Hong Kong and Shanghai Banking Corporation)), as well as reviews of rating agencies on the development of ESG standards, criteria and taxonomies.

Research methods. The methodological basis of the research consisted of general scientific methods and techniques – such as analysis and synthesis, and the integration of historical and logical approaches – as well as specific assessment methods, including the observation of key indicators and expert evaluations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

O. S. Aksinina notes that the social responsibility of business is considered the most essential tool for achieving the country's key goal of long-term socio-economic development. The author defines the possibilities of applying a methodology for assessing the social responsibility of companies based on the use of several indicators at the company level, as well as the potential for combining data into a rating of social responsibility by industry or region [1].

X. Chen et al. investigate the role of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the effectiveness of Chinese companies' investments in Japan. The authors emphasize that CSR has a positive impact on organizational trust, credibility, and risk management, ultimately enhancing investment efficiency [2].

J. M. Ptaschunder believes that the latest economic achievements are aimed at modern micro-, meso-, and macroeconomic analysis of public choice in environmental decision-making. Sustainable finance encompasses a broad range of concepts, including socially responsible investment, climate finance, ESG investments, green finance, carbon finance, and energy finance, among others [3].

S. U. Rahman writes that green finance is an imperative area that addresses modern challenges of economic sustainability by focusing on environmentally responsible investments and promoting sustainable economic growth. The paradigm of a closed-loop economy, supported by green financing, advocates

for the implementation of strategies for recycling and reclaiming resources, which ultimately leads to a reduction in waste production and resource consumption [4].

T. Bagh and K. Iftikhar consider the transformative impact of closed-loop economics practices on green finance, which promotes resource efficiency and waste reduction as an essential component of sustainable growth. The authors propose future research directions and policy considerations to enhance the effectiveness of green finance in fostering the development of an environmentally sustainable economy [5].

R. B. Nozdreva examines innovative forms of investment in the development of environmental projects within the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Particular emphasis is placed on Green Bonds (GBonds), which were introduced in 2007. The author demonstrates that their rapid growth trajectory highlights highly promising prospects for the future [6].

E. Campiglio et al. believe that the macroeconomic and institutional environment, together with an increased understanding of the links between financial dynamics and natural resources, created a new space of opportunities for low-carbon investments and financing [7].

N. Taher and B. Hajjar point out that environmental investments enable the simultaneous achievement of both business and social goals by financing environmentally friendly activities. Investments in clean energy and other ecological goods and services will be crucial for addressing environmental degradation and generating substantial returns for private investors [8].

K. Wendt writes that focusing on the act of charity rather than achieving social outcomes and relying on unpredictable funding prevented numerous charities from reaching their full potential in terms of innovation, efficiency, and scale. According to the author, except for a small number of specialized forms of impact investing, such as social bonds, green bonds, and philanthropy, little is known about the complex interactions between entrepreneurs or organizations, intermediaries, rules for investors, and the successful use of tools in this area [9].

W. Spiess-Knafl & B. Scheck consider investors' justifications for allocating part of their resources to affect investing. One of the key considerations is the interaction between financial and social impact requirements. Both goals are interdependent, and trade-offs may arise when capital providers with different expectations of return participate in financing a social enterprise [10].

J. Tan and J. Wei note that environmental, social, and governance (ESG) indicators are a crucial aspect of responsible investing, drawing global attention from the investment community. The authors propose conclusions for practitioners seeking to optimize productivity in the pharmaceutical manufacturing sector by adhering to sustainable and socially responsible business practices [11].

A. P. Gorbunov et al. note that the public declaration of the ESG agenda does not signify a real opportunity to follow it consistently and in everything: its recognition in conceptual terms and consolidation in legislation is accompanied by problems of its integration into real business activities due to extreme political and economic instability, the general unwillingness of business structures to meaningful, socially transformative changes in their primary goals. [12].

B. S. Akbarova et al. review the system of implementing ESG management in the context of green business in Russia and Central Asian countries, and also substantiate the directions for training and developing relevant skills among entrepreneurs in response to modern labor market demands [13].

K. N. Sonko & M. Sonko draw attention to the opportunities that ESG offers for public-private partnership in Africa [14].

E. Alexandra identifies a positive impact of ESG ratings and their components on the market performance of companies in developed markets. At the same time, this relationship is not yet confirmed in emerging markets [15].

X. Lai et al. examine the relationship between ESG indicators and corporate cash reserves, finding a negative correlation between them. According to the authors, the negative correlation between ESG and corporate cash reserves is more pronounced in private companies, companies with a low level of pollution, and companies with a lower degree of capital market liberalization [16].

S. Y. Pertseva examines the features and types of socially responsible and ethical investment in the context of the green economy, analyzing the development of sustainable investments worldwide. The author concluded that SRI aid protects the interests of future generations by ensuring environmental safety and conservation [17].

Thus, the study and analysis of existing theories and models of socially responsible investment (SRI), as well as concepts of sustainable development and ESG factors (environmental, social and managerial factors), allow understanding the principles and mechanisms of SRI, as well as its role in the global economy.

Collecting and analyzing statistical data on socially responsible investing in various countries, including investment volumes, market dynamics, the effectiveness of investment strategies, and other relevant indicators is necessary.

Analysis of foreign experience helps identify the main problems and challenges faced by investors and companies in implementing SRI, such as the lack of standards for assessing ESG factors, risks associated with legislative changes, and others.

A comparative analysis of the experiences of different countries in the field of SRI is relevant, as it enables us to identify successful practices, features, and differences in approaches to socially responsible investment, while also highlighting factors that influence its development.

RESULTS

Figure 1 Number of ESG funds and their assets in 2010-2020, billion dollars [18]

According to the UNCTAD (at the time of the study, data from the 2021 review is available, summarizing statistics for 2020 inclusive), over the past 10 years, the number of responsible development funds (ESG funds) has increased from 1304 to 3987 (almost 3 times), and about half of all sustainable investment funds have appeared in the last five years [19]. At the same time, over the past five years, the

total income of responsible investment funds has increased fourfold, while in 2020 the assets of such funds have almost doubled (which is explained, among other things, by the COVID-19 pandemic, since the healthcare sector is one of the largest sectors of socially responsible financing) (see Figure 1).

As shown in Figure 1, Europe is the leader in both the number and volume of assets of sustainable investment funds, accounting for about 73% of global ESG funds. North America accounts for approximately 18% of this market, while other regions account for around 10%. At the same time, globally, ESG funds account for no more than 3.5% of all investment fund assets [20].

The conceptual features of the formation and development of socially responsible investment in various countries depend directly on factors such as stock market models, religious and socio-cultural determinants, and the nature of citizens' economic behavior, among others. At the same time, the functioning and development of the SRI market are generally determined by the effective development of its four main components: government regulation, supply availability, demand availability, and the intermediary apparatus. The most critical element in such an ecosystem is government support and regulation of socially responsible investment, which is currently well developed in foreign countries (see Table 1).

Table 1

The primary forms of government support for SRI in foreign countries

Country	Forms of government support	Description
Great Britain	Tax benefits	Social Investment Tax Relief (SITR): 30% of the investment amount (not to exceed 1 million pounds) is returned to investors in the form of a tax deduction
	Access of social enterprises to procurement	The Social Value Act enables social enterprises to participate in tenders for government contracts. Government contracts must necessarily take into account not only economic, but also social and environmental results.
USA	Development of a network of Community Development Financial Institutions (CDFIs)	It supports the activation of the potential of local communities interested in implementing projects aiming to address community challenges and improving quality of life. CDFIs, which include banks, credit unions, venture capital funds, and microfinance organizations, attract capital from both private and institutional investors. Each institution involved in local community development must undergo a certification process by the Community Development Financial Institutions Fund.

	Support for the movement to create public benefit corporations (benefit corporations, B-corporations)	The B-corporation status serves as a guarantee that the company truly adheres to the stated ESG values. To receive a B-Corporation certificate, a company must undergo an independent certification of its environmental and social impact and regularly publish reports on its social and ecological activities verified by an independent evaluator.
Australia	Certification of green bonds according to the Climate Bond Standard	Socially responsible investments are primarily directed towards environmental projects (96% of the country's socially accountable investment volume). The government's attention to "green finance" in the Asia-Pacific region is increasing.
	Use of pension funds	Creation of financial instruments for socially responsible investment to allocate funds to support projects with a documented economic impact and a clear social orientation (for example, in the field of healthcare, housing, and community development).
Canada	Development of intermediary platforms	The OpenImpact and Responsible Investment Marketplace (RI) platforms are created to provide information about investment opportunities in the field of socially responsible investing.
	Investment Training Program for Entrepreneurs (pilot program of the Government of Canada, 2019)	The program involves providing financing in the amount of 10,000-100,000 dollars to socially oriented organizations to pay for the services of verified experts who contribute to the development of such organizations (that is, developing financial models, R&D plans, etc., to attract investment further)
Germany	Development of social, ethical, and green banks	The largest banks and funds in Germany are developing their programs and products for socially responsible investment. Cultural, social, and environmental projects are supported.
	Creation of regional development banks	Supporting regional and municipal authorities in addressing social problems, particularly in creating affordable housing and assisting small and medium-sized businesses. All banks adhere to the principles of ESG development.
China	Government support for the green bond market	Approximately 1,400 incubators and accelerators established for social organizations that offer financing to social enterprises at various stages of development.
	Standardization of requirements	Streamlining internal schemes and rules for regulating the green bond market by international standards
Japan	Formation of a socially responsible investment ecosystem modeled on the UK	Government involvement in the regulation and promotion of ESG investment, as well as the development of an intermediary network, etc.
South Korea	Creation of a special legal structure for social entrepreneurs	Special legal status of social entrepreneurs (subsidies and tax benefits in the first 5 years of work)
	Creation of significant funds for socially responsible investment	Created either by the state with the participation of private investors, or by private investors with the active support of the state.

	Creation and support of a certification system for social enterprises	365 Social Enterprises catalog (formation of prestige and status of a social enterprise, certified participants are invited to all significant events in the country)
India	Special solutions for expanding the market of socially responsible investments	Creation of alternative and socially-oriented funds
Singapore	The financial center of the Asian region, a regional hub for socially responsible investment	The development of sustainable and social exchanges is supported by the Asian Venture Philanthropy Association (AVPN) and numerous regional investment companies operating in Asia, which are based in Singapore.

Source: Compiled by the author based on research [21]

As shown in Table 1, the ecosystem of socially responsible investment support is most developed in the UK, Germany, South Korea, and Canada. Japan and China are also following the path of creating comprehensive support for socially responsible investment. In the United States, numerous investment organizations are engaged in sustainable and responsible investing, encompassing both public and private entities. The SRI market in the United States is also represented by development institutions, as well as special funds for socially responsible investment created by large investment companies and banks. In addition, the USA is also the center of global expertise in the field of responsible investment, with specialized networks uniting market participants (GIIN, Toniic, Investors' Circle) [22].

Recently, business assessments based on ESG factors have become one of the most important and relevant for the development of the responsible investment market. As the SRI industry becomes more sustainable and large-scale, it requires increasingly sophisticated assessment capabilities at every level. To date, several measurement standards have been developed, for example, IRIS, SDGs, and the Impact Management Project, among others; however, none of them are generally accepted [23].

Most efforts and initiatives aimed at assessing the effectiveness of SRI are related to two industry-wide systems. The first is the Impact Reporting and Investment Standards (IRIS) reporting system, a project of the non-profit Global Impact Investing Network (GIIN). IRIS offers a comprehensive vocabulary and a suite of detailed and specific indicators that can be tailored to the unique needs of individual investment funds and organizations. The second assessment system, the Global Impact Rating System (GIIRS), developed by the non-profit laboratory B-Lab (USA), evaluates the social and environmental performance of funds and companies seeking to obtain socially

responsible capital. The B-Lab organization is an independent evaluator organization that awards certificates (B-Lab certification or B-Corporation certification) to companies that meet the criteria of social and environmental effectiveness.

In recent years, the pace of work on developing policies that allow for effective socially responsible investment has accelerated. At the center of these efforts is the Impact Investing Policy Collaborative (IIPC), an international network comprising scientists, practitioners, and policymakers from dozens of countries. The Omidyar Network, which focuses its efforts on expanding microfinance in Asia and elsewhere, distinguishes between three types of participants within sectors: “market scalars” who rapidly expand proven business models; “market innovators” who create and test new technologies and businesses; as well as enterprises and organizations that provide industry infrastructure such as credit ratings and research [24]. Their contribution and effectiveness should be evaluated in different ways. Moreover, the social impact of these actors should be measured not only at the firm level but also as part of the total social impact of the sector as a whole, which in successful cases should be greater than the simple sum of its parts.

DISCUSSION

Despite the long-term development of the foreign market of socially responsible investments and its rapid growth in recent years, the most significant problems in the development of the ESG bond sector are the following:

- lack of clear, generally accepted criteria and methods for ESG standards and SRI performance assessments;
- The use by issuing companies of income from ESG investments not for their intended purpose (i.e., not to finance social and/or environmental projects), but to ensure the operational day-to-day activities of companies (the so-called “greenwashing”).

The lack of a generally accepted comprehensive methodology and methods for assessing and accounting for the allocation of securities and the use of income from them precisely in connection with the ESG agenda has led to the fact that, according to auditors, in recent years the European Commission has overestimated the data on ESG bonds by almost a third – for example, of the 261 billion euros declared for the period 2014-2020, to the ESG market, 72 billion euros had nothing to do with climate protection.

Thus, at present, the key problem of SRI development is the lack of a unified approach to measuring the social and environmental outcomes of socially responsible investments.

In our opinion, the development of various standards for assessing the effectiveness of social impact for classical businesses, start-ups, and institutional organizations in the field of SRI (i.e., SRI development institutions) can become a valuable tool that enables better and more effective socially responsible investment. This is especially true for startups.

Venture capital investors identify several basic characteristics in a startup:

- This is a business focused on exponential growth;
- A startup uses innovative technologies and business models that ultimately change market behavior;
- A startup is a more effective way to do something to get closer to the ideal final result (IFR);
- This is a business with a high degree of uncertainty and risk.

In addition, a startup is, by definition, a commercialized product: an idea, a project, or a business model. If the commercial potential of an idea is not confirmed, it cannot be considered a startup; that is, a non-profit project cannot be classified as a startup, even if it utilizes innovative technologies. However, social entrepreneurship can evolve into a startup if the above characteristics are considered. Startups in the fields of ecology and social entrepreneurship can become truly breakthrough and contribute significantly to the development of the Russian national economy.

A startup is a business aimed at achieving exponential growth. A business idea based on this concept can lead to significant structural shifts in the market, and scaling and replicating a successful idea can yield substantial profits for investors. That is why the assessment of the social contribution of startups should differ from the assessment of the social contribution of “scaling” companies or companies providing institutional development of SRI.

Additionally, in our opinion, to stimulate the development of socially responsible investment in Russia, as outlined in the table. The experience of South Korea, China, and the United Kingdom can be identified as the primary forms of government support. China's experience in creating accelerators (i.e. organizations whose purpose is –intensive development of start-ups through mentoring, training, financial

and expert support in exchange for a share in the capital), providing financing for social enterprises at various stages of business, combined with the development of access for social enterprises to public procurement (as in the UK), as well as the creation of significant funds for socially responsible investment, support for the certification system of social enterprises, formation of their prestige and status (by analogy with South Korea) can significantly contribute to the development of the SRI market in Russia., by developing the national economy and stimulating investment mechanisms.

CONCLUSION

The development of new financial technologies, tools and standards, as well as the gradual entry of new intermediaries into the market, such as management companies and consulting companies, correlate not only with a gradual increase in business social responsibility but also with a cooling interest in the financial markets of developed countries and investors' interest in entering the markets of developing countries that are not yet firmly integrated into the global economy and previously participated very little in global financial processes. From this perspective, the primary objective of socially responsible investment is to reconcile the growing demand for resources with the current supply, which is severely limited due to the non-renewable nature of some resources.

At the present stage, the SRI market is becoming not just another segment of the investment market, but also the result of a change in the business-society-state relationship model, a kind of "auto-calibration tool" to achieve a new point of stable equilibrium of the economic systems of individual states within the global system, contributing, among other things, to solving environmental and social problems – more effective economic development of countries.

REFERENCES

1. Aksinina, O. S. (2023). Approaches to the Analysis of the Socially Responsible Behavior of the Company. In: Mantulenko, V. (eds) *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference Engineering Innovations and Sustainable Development. CEISD 2023. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, vol 378*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-38122-5_68
2. Chen, X., Dong, X., & Ma, C. (2023). Investing with Purpose: The Role of CSR in Enhancing Chinese Firms' Performance in Japan. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy, 15*, 20135–20171. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-01875-3>
3. Puaschunder, J. M. (2023). Environmental Financialization. In: *The Future of Resilient Finance. Sustainable Development Goals Series*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-70000-0_10

org/10.1007/978-3-031-30138-4_5

4. Rahman, S. U., Awan, R. U., & Azam, M. (2023). Green Finance: Tackling Sustainability Challenges in Today's Economy. In: Hunjra, A. I., Goodell, J. W. (eds) *The Palgrave Handbook of Green Finance for Sustainable Development*. Palgrave Studies in Impact Finance. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65756-6_29
5. Bagh, T., & Iftikhar, K. (2023). Understanding the Theoretical Context of Green Finance. In: Hunjra, A. I., Goodell, J. W. (eds) *The Palgrave Handbook of Green Finance for Sustainable Development*. Palgrave Studies in Impact Finance. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65756-6_3
6. Nozdreva, R. B. (2022). Green Bonds in the System of International Environmental Financing of Industry 4.0 Projects. In: Zavyalova, E. B., Popkova, E. G. (eds) *Industry 4.0*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79496-5_26
7. Campiglio, E., Godin, A., Kemp-Benedict, E., & Matikainen, S. (2017). The Tightening Links Between Financial Systems and the Low-Carbon Transition. In: Arestis, P., Sawyer, M. (eds) *Economic Policies since the Global Financial Crisis. International Papers in Political Economy*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60459-6_8
8. Taher, N., & Hajjar, B. (2014). Environmental Investments. In: *Energy and Environment in Saudi Arabia: Concerns & Opportunities*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02982-5_3
9. Wendt, K. (2023). From ESG to Impact Investing, Taxonomies, and Sustainable Development Goals. In: Wendt, K., Villhauer, B. (eds) *Sustainable Wealth Management. Sustainable Finance*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-55505-3_2
10. Spiess-Knafl, W., & Scheck, B. (2023). Impact Investing. In: *Impact Investing. Palgrave Studies in Impact Finance*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32183-2_3
11. Tan, J., & Wei, J. (2023). Configurational Analysis of ESG Performance, Innovation Intensity, and Financial Leverage: A Study on Total Factor Productivity in Chinese Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15, 13803–13827. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01678-y>
12. Gorbunov, A. P., Gorbunova, N. N., Gorbunova, M. A., & May-Boroda, G. N. (2023). Problems of Implementing the ESG Agenda as a Modern Guideline for Business and Investment Management and Ways to Solve Them. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) *ESG Management of the Development of the Green Economy in Central Asia. Environmental Footprints and Eco-design of Products and Processes*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-46525-3_4
13. Akbarova, B. S., Cheglakova, L. S., Kopytina, Y. A., Ivanova, I. G., & Popova, Y. N. (2023). Entrepreneurial Education and Development of Entrepreneurial Skills During ESG Management of Green Business in Russia and Central Asia. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) *ESG Management of the Development of the Green Economy in Central Asia. Environmental Footprints and Eco-design of Products and Processes*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-46525-3_29
14. Sonko, K. N., & Sonko, M. (2023). ESG in Africa: Relevance and Applicability. In: *Demystifying Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG)*. Palgrave Studies in Impact Finance. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35867-8_2
15. Aleksandra, E. (2023). The Influence of ESG Factors on the Company's Performance in Developed and Emerging Markets. In: Bilgin, M. H., Danis, H., Demir, E., Aykac Alp, E., Çankaya, S. (eds) *Eurasian Business and Economics Perspectives. EBES 2022. Eurasian Studies in Business and Economics*, 27. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-51212-4_1
16. Lai, X., Quan, L., & Guo, C. et al. (2023). Can ESG reconcile the conflicting motives of cash holding? Evidence from China. *Empirical Economics*, 68, 1719–1756. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-024-02691-z>
17. Pertseva, S. Y. (2022). Socially Responsible Investing in the Context of a Green Economy. In: Zavyalova, E. B., Popkova, E. G. (eds) *Industry 4.0*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79496-5_8
18. Compiled by the author based on data from: *Socially Responsible and ESG Funds*. Available at: <https://mutualfunds.com/categories/all-funds/strategy-funds/socially-responsible-and-esg-funds> (accessed 20 April 2023).

19. *World Investment Report-2021. Investing in sustainable recovery: an overview / UNCTAD.* Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/wir2021_overview_ru.pdf (accessed 20 April 2023).
20. *Responsible Investment Review 2021 / HSBC Holdings plc (Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation).* Available at: <http://www.assetmanagement.hsbc.com.hk/> (accessed 20 April 2023).
21. Ermakova, E. P. (2022). Legal regulation of “responsible” investment in Russia and foreign countries: concept, principles, examples. *Bulletin of Perm University. Legal Sciences*, 55, 86–106. (in Russ.)
22. Altukhova, E. V. (2021). The stock market as a catalyst for ESG transformation. *Management and Business Administration*, 4, 111–117. (in Russ.)
23. Ten, D. E., & Pokushalov, A. V. (2021). ESG criteria in investing: global trends and prospects for the development of the Russian market of “socially responsible” investments. *Issues of Sustainable development of society*, 7, 44–49. (in Russ.)
24. Avramov Doron, Cheng Si, Lioui Abraham, & Tarelli Andrea. Sustainable investing with ESG rating uncertainty. *Journal of Financial Economics*. 2021. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304405X21003974> (accessed 20 April 2023).

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